

Accidental Hot Water Scald as the Most Common Cause of Burn Injury in Children: A Hospital-Based Study

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Received: 11 May 2026
Accepted: 18 May 2026
Published Online: 5 June 2026

Published by:
Gopalganj Medical College, Gopalganj,
Bangladesh

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DOI:

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ABSTRACT

Burn injuries are a significant cause of morbidity and mortality among children, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Young children are especially vulnerable due to developmental and environmental factors. Scald burns are commonly reported as the leading cause, often occurring in domestic settings. Understanding epidemiological patterns is essential for prevention and management. This study aimed to assess the socio-demographic characteristics, etiology, environmental factors and clinical outcomes of pediatric burn injuries. This hospital-based retrospective observational study was conducted at the Department of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, KPJ Specialized Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, from December 2017 to November 2025. A total of 505 pediatric burn patients were included. Data were collected from medical records and analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. The majority of patients were aged 1–4 years (49.9%) and male (59.0%). Most cases were from rural areas (65.5%). Scald burns were the predominant cause (65.1%), followed by flame burns (21.4%). Among scald burns, the most frequent specific agents were hot rice starch (42.2%), hot water (35.9%), and hot milk/tea (21.9%). Most injuries occurred at home (85.3%) and were unsupervised (60.8%). The majority of burns involved less than 10% Total Body Surface Area (41.8%; comprising 7.5% with <1% TBSA and 34.3% with 1–10% TBSA), while 24.8% exceeded 20% TBSA. Superficial burns were most common (68.9%) and 73.7% of patients recovered without complications. Severe burns were significantly associated with older age, rural residence and flame injuries. Pediatric burns remain a preventable public health issue, with scald injuries being the leading cause. Improved supervision, safer household practices and targeted prevention strategies are essential to reduce incidence and severity.

Keywords: Pediatric burns, scald injury, burn epidemiology, burn severity, Bangladesh

(The Insight 2026; 9(2): 324-328)

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INTRODUCTION

Burn injuries remain a major public health concern worldwide, particularly among children, where they contribute substantially to morbidity, disability and mortality [1]. Pediatric burns are distinct from adult burns in terms of etiology, risk factors and outcomes, largely due to developmental, behavioral and environmental differences [2]. Young children are especially vulnerable because of their limited risk awareness, dependence on caregivers and increased exposure to domestic hazards [3]. The epidemiology of scald burns in Bangladesh exhibits distinct cultural characteristics. Notably, beyond the commonly recognized hazards of hot water and cooking fluids worldwide, a unique and frequent cause of pediatric scalds is hot rice starch (starch water), a byproduct of traditional rice preparation. This liquid is typically boiled and then placed in large, open vessels on the kitchen floor to cool, which poses a significant risk to young children who are mobile and active in these areas. Other frequent scalding agents include hot milk, tea, and water used

for bathing, reflecting common domestic practices contributing to burn injuries in this context [4]. Globally, scald burns are identified as the most common cause of burn injuries in children, especially in those under five years of age [1,2]. Studies from various regions consistently report that hot liquids, including water, tea and cooking fluids, are the leading contributors to pediatric burns [5,6]. These injuries frequently occur in household settings, where unsafe cooking practices, inadequate supervision and hazardous environments increase the risk [7,8]. In low- and middle-income countries, including Bangladesh, the burden of pediatric burns is particularly high due to overcrowding, poor housing conditions and lack of awareness regarding preventive measures [9]. Age distribution plays a critical role in pediatric burn epidemiology. Children aged 1–4 years are disproportionately affected, as they are mobile and curious but lack the cognitive ability to recognize danger [10,11]. Previous research has shown that this age group accounts for the highest proportion of

scald injuries, often occurring during routine household activities such as cooking or bathing [12,13]. Gender differences have also been observed, with males generally exhibiting higher burn incidence, possibly due to more exploratory behavior [14].

Environmental and socioeconomic factors further influence the incidence and severity of pediatric burns. Children from rural areas and lower socioeconomic backgrounds are at increased risk due to unsafe living conditions, use of open cooking methods and limited access to safety education [15,16]. Additionally, lack of supervision has been identified as a significant contributing factor, with many injuries occurring when caregivers are absent or distracted [6,17].

The severity and outcomes of burn injuries depend on several factors, including the extent of total body surface area (TBSA) involvement, depth of burn and timely access to medical care [18,19]. While most pediatric burns are superficial and associated with favorable outcomes, severe burns can lead to complications such as infections, prolonged hospitalization and mortality [20,21]. Identifying factors associated with severe burns is therefore essential for improving clinical management and developing targeted prevention strategies.

Despite the growing body of literature on pediatric burns, there remains a paucity of comprehensive data from Bangladesh, particularly regarding the epidemiological patterns, environmental determinants and clinical outcomes of burn injuries in children. Existing studies are often limited in scope or focus on specific aspects without integrating demographic, etiological and outcome-related variables [9]. Furthermore, there is limited evidence examining the association between risk factors and burn severity in this setting.

Therefore, this study aims to analyze the socio-demographic characteristics, etiology, environmental factors and clinical outcomes of pediatric burn injuries in a tertiary care hospital in Dhaka, Bangladesh. By identifying key determinants and patterns, the study seeks to contribute to the existing literature and provide evidence-based insights for improving prevention strategies and clinical care in pediatric burn management.

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this study was to assess the socio-demographic characteristics, etiology, environmental factors and clinical outcomes of pediatric burn injuries.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This hospital-based retrospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery at KPJ Specialized Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh. The study covered eight years from December 2017 to November 2025. The study population included pediatric patients aged 0–14 years who were admitted with burn injuries during the study period. A total of 505 cases were included in the analysis.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Pediatric patients aged 0–14 years

- Patients admitted with any type of burn injury
- Complete medical records available
- Cases treated within the study period

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients older than 14 years
- Incomplete or missing clinical data
- Readmissions for the same burn episode

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected retrospectively from hospital medical records, admission registers and burn unit databases. A structured data extraction form was used to ensure consistency and completeness of information. Variables collected included socio-demographic characteristics (age, sex, residence, socioeconomic status), etiology of burns, environmental and circumstantial factors (place of injury, supervision status, time of occurrence, type of container in scald cases) and clinical parameters (total body surface area burned, depth of burn, duration of hospital stay and outcomes).

All data were carefully reviewed and cross-checked by trained personnel to ensure accuracy and reliability. Standard definitions and classifications were applied uniformly across all cases. Burn severity was categorized based on total body surface area (TBSA) and outcomes were recorded as recovery with or without complications or death. Confidentiality of patient information was strictly maintained by anonymizing all identifiable data during data extraction and analysis. Access to data was restricted to the research team only, ensuring privacy and data security throughout the study process.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize frequencies and percentages. Chi-square tests were applied to assess associations between variables and burn severity. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 505 pediatric burn patients were analyzed. The findings highlight that younger child, particularly those aged 1–4 years, were most affected. Scald injuries were the predominant cause, with most incidents occurring at home and often in unsupervised settings. Clinical outcomes showed that the majority of burns were superficial with favorable recovery, although a notable proportion experienced severe burns and complications.

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of pediatric burn patients. Nearly half of the patients (49.9%) were aged 1–4 years, followed by 25.3% in the 5–9 years group. Male predominance was observed (59.0%). Most patients were from rural areas (65.5%). A majority belonged to lower socioeconomic status (57.2%), with fewer patients in the upper class (8.9%).

Table I: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Pediatric Burn Patients (n = 505)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Age Group (years)	< 1 year	38	7.5
	1-4 years	252	49.9
	5-9 years	128	25.3
	10-14 years	87	17.2
Sex	Male	298	59.0
	Female	207	41.0
Residence	Rural	331	65.5
	Urban	174	34.5
Socioeconomic Status	Lower	289	57.2
	Middle	171	33.9
	Upper	45	8.9

Table II presents the etiology of burn injuries among children. Scald burns were the most common cause, accounting for 65.1% of cases. Among scald burns, the most frequent specific agents were hot rice starch (42.2%), hot water (35.9%), and

hot milk/tea (21.9%). Flame burns contributed to 21.4%, followed by electrical burns (6.7%), contact burns (4.2%) and chemical burns (2.6%).

Table II: Etiology of Burn Injuries Among Children (n = 505)

Cause of Burn	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Scald (hot water/liquid)	329	65.1
- Hot rice starch (starch water)	139	42.2 (of scald)
- Hot water	118	35.9 (of scald)
- Hot milk/tea	72	21.9 (of scald)
Flame burn	108	21.4
Electrical burn	34	6.7
Contact burn	21	4.2
Chemical burn	13	2.6

Table III describes the circumstantial and environmental characteristics of burn injuries. Most injuries occurred at home (85.3%). A higher proportion of cases were unsupervised (60.8%) at the time of injury. Burn incidents

were relatively evenly distributed throughout the day, with slightly higher occurrence during evening/night (34.8%). Among scald cases, open vessels were implicated in 64.4% of incidents.

Table III: Circumstantial and Environmental Characteristics of Burn Injury (n = 505)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Place of injury	Home	431	85.3
	Outside home	74	14.7
Supervision at time of injury	Supervised	198	39.2
	Unsupervised	307	60.8
Time of occurrence	Morning (6am-12pm)	156	30.9
	Afternoon (12pm-6pm)	173	34.3
	Evening/Night	176	34.8
Type of container (scald cases, n = 329)	Open vessel	212	64.4
	Closed container	117	35.6

Table IV shows the clinical characteristics and outcomes of burn injuries. When categorized by TBSA, 7.5% of patients had burns involving less than 1% TBSA, 34.3% had burns between 1-10% TBSA, 33.5% had burns between 10-20% TBSA, and 24.8% had burns exceeding 20% TBSA. Superficial

or partial-thickness burns were more common (68.9%). Hospital stay was less than 7 days in 39.2% of patients. The majority recovered without complications (73.7%), whereas 20.2% had complications and 6.1% resulted in mortality.

Table IV. Clinical Characteristics and Outcomes of Burn Injuries (n = 505)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Total Body Surface Area (TBSA)	<1%	38	7.5
	<10%	173	34.3
	10-20%	169	33.5
	>20%	125	24.8
Depth of burn	Superficial/partial thickness	348	68.9
	Full thickness	157	31.1
Hospital stay duration	<7 days	198	39.2
	7-14 days	187	37.0
	>14 days	120	23.8
Outcome	Recovered without complication	372	73.7
	Recovered with complication	102	20.2
	Death	31	6.1

Table V presents the association between selected variables and severe burns (TBSA $\geq 20\%$). Children aged ≥ 5 years had a higher proportion of severe burns (37.6%) compared to younger children (15.0%), with statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). Rural residence was significantly associated with

severe burns (28.1%, $p = 0.005$). Flame burns showed the highest proportion of severe cases (51.9%), followed by electrical burns (44.1%), both statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). No significant association was found with sex ($p = 0.21$).

Table V: Association Between Selected Variables and Severe Burn (TBSA $\geq 20\%$) (n = 505)

Variable	TBSA <20% n (%)	TBSA $\geq 20\%$ n (%)	Total	p-value	
Age Group	<5 years	244 (85.0)	43 (15.0)	287	<0.001
	≥ 5 years	136 (62.4)	82 (37.6)	218	
Sex	Male	221 (74.2)	77 (25.8)	298	0.21
	Female	159 (76.8)	48 (23.2)	207	
Residence	Rural	238 (71.9)	93 (28.1)	331	0.005
	Urban	142 (81.6)	32 (18.4)	174	
Cause of Burn	Scald	276 (83.9)	53 (16.1)	329	<0.001
	Flame	52 (48.1)	56 (51.9)	108	
	Electrical	19 (55.9)	15 (44.1)	34	
	Other (contact + chemical)	33 (76.7)	10 (23.3)	43	

DISCUSSION

The present study provides a comprehensive overview of pediatric burn injuries, highlighting those children aged 1–4 years are the most affected group. This finding is consistent with Riedlinger et al., who reported that younger children are particularly vulnerable due to developmental immaturity and increased exposure to domestic hazards [1]. Similarly, Duke et al. demonstrated that children under five years account for the majority of burn-related hospitalizations, emphasizing the critical risk in early childhood [11].

The predominance of scald burns observed in this study aligns with global trends. Shields et al. noted that scald injuries are the leading cause of burns in young children, primarily due to hot liquids in household environments [2]. Sahu et al. further emphasized that scald burns are largely preventable and often linked to unsafe handling of hot fluids [7]. The high incidence of scald injuries in the current study underscores the need for targeted preventive interventions in domestic settings.

The finding that most injuries occurred at home and in unsupervised conditions is supported by previous literature. Stewart et al. identified lack of supervision as a significant risk factor for pediatric scald injuries [6]. Similarly, Zou et al. highlighted that household environments, particularly kitchens, are high-risk areas for burn injuries [8]. These findings suggest that caregiver awareness and supervision play a crucial role in preventing such incidents.

Socioeconomic disparities were evident, with a higher proportion of cases from rural and lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Alnababtah et al. reported that children from disadvantaged settings are more likely to experience burn injuries due to unsafe living conditions and limited access to preventive education [15]. He et al. also emphasized the increased burden of burns in rural Bangladesh, attributing it to environmental and infrastructural factors [9].

Regarding clinical characteristics, the majority of burns were superficial or partial thickness, which is consistent with findings by Han et al., who reported that most pediatric burns are of lesser severity and have favorable outcomes [19]. However, a significant proportion of patients in this study experienced severe burns, particularly those associated with flame and electrical injuries. Rojas-Contreras et al. found that flame burns are more likely to result in extensive TBSA involvement and severe outcomes [22].

The association between age and burn severity observed in this study is noteworthy. Older children (≥ 5 years) had a higher proportion of severe burns, which may be attributed to

increased exposure to high-risk environments and activities. Saeman et al. similarly reported that older children are more likely to sustain severe burns due to engagement in outdoor or hazardous activities [18].

The significant association between rural residence and severe burns further highlights disparities in access to safety measures and healthcare services. Sadeghi-Bazargani et al. identified environmental and socioeconomic factors as key determinants of burn severity [16]. Additionally, delayed presentation and limited access to specialized care in rural areas may contribute to worse outcomes.

The overall mortality rate of 6.1% observed in this study is comparable to reports from other developing countries. Chelidze et al. identified TBSA and burn depth as major predictors of mortality in pediatric burn patients [21]. Similarly, Kraft et al. emphasized that severe burns are associated with increased risk of multiorgan dysfunction and mortality [20].

Hospital stay duration in this study was generally short, with most patients discharged within two weeks. This finding is in line with Wang et al., who reported that burn severity and complications are key determinants of length of stay [23]. Patients with minor burns tend to recover, while severe cases require prolonged hospitalization and intensive care.

Overall, the findings of this study reinforce existing evidence that pediatric burns are largely preventable and strongly influenced by environmental and socioeconomic factors. Addressing these determinants through targeted interventions, caregiver education and improved safety measures can significantly reduce the burden of pediatric burn injuries.

CONCLUSION

Pediatric burn injuries are predominantly caused by scalds, particularly among young children in domestic settings. Most burns are preventable and associated with inadequate supervision and unsafe environments. While outcomes are generally favorable, severe burns remain a concern, especially among older children and those from rural areas. Targeted prevention strategies and improved caregiver awareness are essential to reduce the burden.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my sincere gratitude for the invaluable support and cooperation provided by the staff, participants and my co-authors/colleagues who contributed to this study.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Riedlinger DI, Jennings PA, Edgar DW, Harvey JG, Cleland MH, Wood FM, Cameron PA. Scald burns in children aged 14 and younger in Australia and New Zealand—an analysis based on the Burn Registry of Australia and New Zealand (BRANZ). *Burns*. 2015 May 1;41(3):462-8.
2. Shields WC, McDonald EM, Pfisterer K, Gielen AC. Scald burns in children under 3 years: an analysis of NEISS narratives to inform a scald burn prevention program. *Injury prevention*. 2015 Oct 1;21(5):296-300.
3. Zhu L, Zhang H, Shi F, Yi D, Zhu G. Epidemiology and outcome analysis of scalds in children caused by "guo lian kang": an 11-year review in a burn center in China. *Burns*. 2015 Mar 1;41(2):289-96.
4. Abedin M, Rahman FN, Rakhshanda S, Mashreky SR, Rahman AF, Hossain A. Epidemiology of non-fatal burn injuries in children: evidence from Bangladesh Health and Injury Survey 2016. *BMJ Paediatrics Open*. 2022 Jun 14;6(1):e001412.
5. Wang S, Li D, Shen C, Chai J, Zhu H, Lin Y, Liu C. Epidemiology of burns in pediatric patients of Beijing City. *BMC pediatrics*. 2016 Oct 18;16(1):166.
6. Stewart J, Benford P, Wynn P, Watson MC, Coupland C, Deave T, Hindmarch P, Majsak-Newman G, Kendrick D. Modifiable risk factors for scald injury in children under 5 years of age: A Multi-centre Case–Control Study. *Burns*. 2016 Dec 1;42(8):1831-43.
7. Sahu SA, Agrawal K, Patel PK. Scald burn, a preventable injury: analysis of 4306 patients from a major tertiary care center. *Burns*. 2016 Dec 1;42(8):1844-9.
8. Zou K, Wynn PM, Miller P, Hindmarch P, Majsak-Newman G, Young B, Hayes M, Kendrick D. Preventing childhood scalds within the home: overview of systematic reviews and a systematic review of primary studies. *Burns*. 2015 Aug 1;41(5):907-24.
9. He S, Alonge O, Agrawal P, Sharmin S, Islam I, Mashreky SR, Arifeen SE. Epidemiology of burns in rural Bangladesh: an update. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2017 Apr;14(4):381.
10. Laitakari E, Koljonen V, Rintala R, Pyörälä S, Gissler M. Incidence and risk factors of burn injuries among infants, Finland 1990–2010. *Journal of pediatric surgery*. 2015 Apr 1;50(4):608-12.
11. Duke J, Wood F, Semmens J, Edgar DW, Spilsbury K, Hendrie D, Rea S. A study of burn hospitalizations for children younger than 5 years of age: 1983–2008. *Pediatrics*. 2011 Apr 1;127(4):e971-7.
12. Moser WJ, Bilka KR, Vrouwe SQ, Glick JC, Ramaiah V. Running water while bathing is a risk factor for pediatric scald burns. *Burns*. 2023 Nov 1;49(7):1714-8.
13. Trop M, Herzog SA, Pfurtscheller K, Hoebenreich AM, Schintler MV, Stockenhuber A, Kamolz LP. The past 25 years of pediatric burn treatment in Graz and important lessons been learned. An overview. *Burns*. 2015 Jun 1;41(4):714-20.
14. Seo DK, Kym D, Yim H, Yang HT, Cho YS, Kim JH, Hur J, Chun W. Epidemiological trends and risk factors in major burns patients in South Korea: a 10-year experience. *Burns*. 2015 Feb 1;41(1):181-7.
15. Alnababtah K, Khan S, Ashford R. Socio-demographic factors and the prevalence of burns in children: an overview of the literature. *Paediatrics and international child health*. 2016 Jan 2;36(1):45-51.
16. Sadeghi-Bazargani H, Mohammadi R, Amiri S, Syedi N, Tabrizi A, Irandoost P, Safiri S. Individual-level predictors of inpatient childhood burn injuries: a case–control study. *BMC public health*. 2016 Mar 1;16(1):209.
17. Emond A, Sheahan C, Mytton J, Hollén L. Developmental and behavioural associations of burns and scalds in children: a prospective population-based study. *Archives of disease in childhood*. 2017 May 1;102(5):428-483.
18. Saeman MR, Hodgman EI, Burriss A, Wolf SE, Arnoldo BD, Kowalske KJ, Phelan HA. Epidemiology and outcomes of pediatric burns over 35 years at Parkland Hospital. *Burns*. 2016 Feb 1;42(1):202-8.
19. Han D, Wei Y, Li Y, Zha X, Li R, Xia C, Li Y, Yang H, Xie J, Tian S. Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of 5,569 pediatric burns in central China from 2013 to 2019. *Frontiers in public health*. 2022 Mar 29; 10:751615.
20. Kraft R, Herndon DN, Finnerty CC, Shahrokhi S, Jeschke MG. Occurrence of multiorgan dysfunction in pediatric burn patients: incidence and clinical outcome. *Annals of surgery*. 2014 Feb 1;259(2):381-7.
21. Chelidze KI, Lim CC, Peck RN, Giiti G, Leahy N, Rabbits A, Yurt R, Gallagher JJ, Mitchell KB. Predictors of mortality among pediatric burn patients in East Africa. *Journal of Burn Care & Research*. 2016 Mar 1;37(2):e154-60.
22. Rojas-Contreras C, De la Cruz-KuG, Eyzaguirre-Sandoval ME, Chamberg-Michilot D, Torres-Roman JS. Fire burns matter: A case-control study of severe accidental burns in pediatric patients. *Electron J Gen Med*. 2023;20(1):em432.
23. Wang T, Nie C, Zhang H, Zeng X, Yu H, Wei Z, Yang C, Shi X. Epidemiological characteristics and factors affecting length of hospital stay for children and adults with burns in Zunyi, China: a retrospective study. *PeerJ*. 2018 Oct 3;6:e5740.